

GEOLOGICAL FIELDWORK REPORT ON

Changotang Anticline , Along Matiranga – Khagrachari Roadcut Section

Report submitted in requirement of partial fulfilment of the syllabus for the 2nd year B.S. (Honours)

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Abstract

This report provides an overview of fieldwork conducted in Khagrachari and the Changotang Anticline.

This is an outline of the geological and lithological analyses of an organized fieldwork that was investigated in the Changotang anticline by respective faculty members from the Department of Geology and second year undergraduate students studying at the mentioned department of University of Dhaka.

The time frame in which the fieldwork was accomplished out was from the 25th March to the 31st March in the year 2022.

These seven days of fieldwork were fully committed to the identification of topographic and geomorphologic features, with a particular emphasis on lithological description, including litho-stratigraphic succession, sedimentary structures, georesources, and geohazards. The identification of these features has been the major focus of the fieldwork. This work was accomplished with the goal of achieving something that would require knowledge from various fields of study.

The Changotang anticline could well be found on the western side of the Chittagong–Tripura folded belt. It is oriented in the opposite direction as the Chittagong–Tripura folded belt, running from north to south.

This type of formation is referred to as a thrust anticline when considering its structural characteristics. Along this anticline, which is the region that is the subject of the research that is currently being done, there may be exposures of the Surma group, Upper marine shale, Tipam sandstone formation, Dupitila formation, and alluvium from the most recent years.

The Miocene period continued all the way through to the Plio-Pleistocene, during which time these rocks were being formed.

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Chapter 1 : Introduction

1. Introduction

The Bengal basin, which constituted Bangladesh and a region of eastern India, is one of the least explored and most widely known basins in the world. In the late Mesozoic, the splitting of Gondwanaland initiated the uninterrupted geological expansion of this basin. The Indo-Burman ranges to the east, the Shillong Plateau to the north, and exposures of the Indian craton to the west designate the larger Bengal basin.

These hills are a part of the Arakan-Yoma Frontal Folded Belts. This paper attempts to present an explanation of the tectonic framework, stratigraphy, drainage, geomorphology, depositional history, and economic geology of the Rangamati field area and the southeastern part of Bangladesh.

1.1 Objectives

Field study is mostly about learning about geology. It uses methods and techniques to look at the outcrop's structure, physical features, stratigraphy, and materials. The eastern and, more importantly, the southeastern part of Bangladesh is very complicated and shows a lot of how the Bengal basin's tectonics have changed over time. The Frontal Fold belt is one of the most important parts of the Bengal basin's geology. The rocks here are from the Miocene to the Pliocene eras. On the other hand, the area is bad because it doesn't have any oil. Geologists are still very interested in the area. Huge piles of sediments are exposed so that they can be studied and help us learn more about how complicated nature is. Our main goal was to look at and learn about the area's history of sedimentation, structure, stratigraphy, fossils, depositional environment, and economic geology. We also wanted to make a geological map of the area.

The purposes can be summarized as follows:

- Generating a geological map of a region.
- Determination of sedimentary structures and lithology.
- Development of a stratigraphic column
- Research into the formation of the column
- Analysis of sedimentary formations and other structural characteristics.
- Interpretation of the region's geologic history.
- Prediction of the region's economic significance.

It should be mentioned that, despite the researched area's expansiveness, more detailed examinations were not possible due to the extremely limited timespan.

1.2 Study Area

1.2.1 Location and Extent of the Study area

This entire fieldwork was undertaken in the Changoatong anticline, which is located in the Khagrachari area in Bangladesh's southeast. Khagrachari district (Fig 1.2) is bordered on the north by the Indian state of Tripura, on the south by Rangamati and Chittagong districts, on the east by Rangamati district, and on the west by Chittagong district and the Indian state of Tripura.

The study region is bounded by latitudes between $23^{\circ}02'30.12''\text{N}$ and $23^{\circ}8'11.11''\text{N}$ and longitudes between $91^{\circ}52'23''\text{E}$ and $92^{\circ}00'02''\text{E}$. This region is geographically located in the western portion of the Chittagong hill tracts (CHT). (Fig 1.1)

Fig 1.1 : Map of Bangladesh (Source: Google Earth)

Fig 1.2 : Map of khagrachari District (Source: Banglapedia)

Fig 1.3 : The study area of the fieldwork at Changotang anticline at Knagrachari conducted by the 2nd year undergraduate students of the University of Dhaka. (Source: Google Earth)

Fig 1.4 : Base camp area

1.2.2 Population and Culture

In Khagrachari, there are not a lot of people living there. According to the survey done in 2011, there are a total of 6,13,917 people living there, with a yearly growth rate of 1.54%; 3,13,793 males, 300,124 females, 3,82,849 Muslims, 89,102 Hindus, 1,39,603 Buddhists, 2,156 Christians, and 207 people of other faiths.

There are also 207 people who do not identify with any religion. Numerous indigenous peoples call this part of the world home, including the Rakhine, Chakma (Fig 1.5 & 1.6), Marma, as well as the Tipra/Tripuri (Tripura). In 2011, there were 316,987 indigenous people living in the district, which accounted for 51.63 percent of the total population. The population density was 220 persons per square kilometer.

Some communities are located in the hills, despite the fact that the vast majority of the people lives in the lowlands. The Jhum culture (Fig 1.7) is the primary means through which the indigenous people support themselves financially. There are also a great number of people here who belong to a wide variety of professions.

Fig 1.5 : Local tribal

Fig 1.6 : Local tribal People (Marma)

Fig 1.6 : Local tribal People (Chakma)

Fig 1.7 : Jhum Cultivation

1.2.3 Weather and Climate

The weather was in a mixed environment. It was mostly sunny but we faced rain on day 1 of our study. On March 26, (Fig 1.8) there was partial cloud cover and a high of 31°C and unpredictable winds. We encountered sudden rain at station 2 on the fieldwork day, March 27, (Fig 1.9) and as soon as we could, we took cover in a nearby shelter. It wasn't there for very long before we resumed our fieldwork. From then on, weather conditions were predominantly sunny or cloudy.

Fig 1.8 : Field Day 1

Fig 1.9 : Cloudy Weather

1.3 Field Methods

The road-cut area, where the rocks are being well exposed, was the site of the examinations and investigations.

The traversing method was employed for field surveying. This technique used a technique called stepping to determine distance. Subsequently, the number of steps was transformed into feet. Each team had one member keep a step count. Since we had a global positioning system (GPS) to determine our position in space, we didn't have to worry too much about steepness. A clinometer was also used to determine the angle at which the beds were placed. For a better understanding of the Khagrachari region, the data was overlaid on the base map, transforming it into a geological map. Each section was broken down into a series of places in the field notebook based on criteria such as ideal exposures, measuring the attitude of bed, collecting samples, identifying main and minor structural lithology of the surrounding physical features, etc. Every area and appropriate geologic features were photographed.

Fig 1.10 : Working in the field

During fieldwork, the following equipment was used:

- **GPS:** To find distinct section's longitude, latitude, and altitude.
- **Clinometers:** In order to measure the bed's dip, strike, and degree of dip, clinometers were used
- **Hammer & Scraper:** To gather samples and identify the right sedimentary and bed formations.
- **Measuring tape:** To determine the thickness of exposures.
- **Pocket lenses:** To examine the surface texture of the rocks
- **Acid bottle:** Its contents, HCl, are employed to detect the presence of calcareous components in rock bodies.
- **Grain Scale:** In order to evaluate sediment grain sizes
- **Field Notebook:** To document the observations we encountered in the field.
- **Base Map:** To make a geological map from the information collected in the field.
- **Sample Bag:** To keep the collected sample safe and organised throughout the field

Fig 1.11 Clinometer

Fig 1.12 Hammer & Scraper

Fig 1.13 Measuring tape

Fig 1.14 Brush

Fig 1.15 Grain Scale

Fig 1.16 Pocket lens

Fig 1.17 **Field Notebook**

Fig 1.18 **Base Map**

Fig 1.19 **Sample Bag**

Chapter 2. Geomorphology

2.1 Topography and drainage pattern

Topography : The topography of Khagrachari is naturally hilly area. Khagrachari is one of the most naturally rich areas with hills , forests and falls etc in Bangladesh. The study area of our fieldwork which is “Changotang Anticline , Along Matiranga-Khagrachari Road cut Section” is mainly a hilly region.

Fig 2.1: Elevation Map of Study Area [Source : www.en-gb.topographic-map.com]

The study area is a steep terrain located beneath the Chittagong hill tracts. The hill range is known as the “Changotang Hill Ranges” and it contains of hills , spurs and cliffs with many other features.

The Changotang Anticline is situated at a great height above the sea level. It varies in elevation and ranges from 60 to 1250 feet above sea level.

Fig 2.2 : Hill Ranges of Khagrachari

Drainage Pattern : Chengi River is the main river that flows through the study area. There are three main rivers that are flowing in Khagrachari – Chengi River , Kasalong River and Maini River. Chengi river is the largest and Maini river is the longest river flowing through Khagrachari and all three main rivers falls into Kaptai Lake.

A number of small streams originating in the eastern hills of Tripura (India) meet at Panchhari (Khagrachari). The combined flow formed Chengi and flows south through Panchhari, Khagrachari, Mahalchari (Khagrachari) and falls into Kaptai Lake near Nannerchar (Rangamati). This is also a flashy river and has a length of about 85 km. [Source : [Banglapedia](#)]

Fig 2.3 : Rivers of Khagrachari [Source : [Bandarban Tours & GeoDASH](#)]

The Chengi river controls the drainage system of our field area. There are some seasonal , intermittent and permanent streams and streamlets also drain the surveyed area which are known as the “Char” locally. These rivers have both dendritic and meandering pattern.

Fig 2.4 : Chengi River

2.2 Geomorphic features

Geomorphic features are geomorphological and topographic landform which can be seen on earth surface. During the field work at “Changotang Anticline , Along Matiranga-Khagrachari Road cut Section” , we observed different types of geomorphic features. Some of which are observed from satellite imagery and some are seen at field. Some of them are defined below :

1. **Stream** : A stream is a body of water or any other moving liquid under the influence of gravity to lower levels in a narrow , clearly defined natural channel is called stream.

Stream has three important roles in the formation of many geomorphic features. Stream erodes the channels in which it flows , it transports materials by weathering and erosion and produces a variety of both erosional and depositional landforms.

Fig 2.5: Stream Doilachara

Chengi River(Fig 2.6), Doilachara (Fig 2.5) and Thakurchara(Fig 2.7) etc were the streams in our study area.

Fig 2.6: Stream Chengi

Fig 2.7: Stream Thakurchara

2. **Valley** : A valley is a depression or low area between hills which often contains a river body or water bodies which running through it. (Fig 2.8)
Our study area contains Chengi Valley.

Fig 2.8: Valley

- Ridge:** A ridge or mountain ridge is a type of landform that is made up of a chain of mountains or hills that form a long, continuous high crest. Both sides of the narrow top of the ridge slope away from it. (Fig 2.9)

Fig 2.9: Ridge

- Waterfall:** A waterfall is a river or body of water steep fall over a rocky ledge into a plunge pool below. In waterfall, water drops abruptly and nearly vertically. Waterfalls represent major interruptions in river flow. Because of the force of water all waterfalls must necessarily be relatively ephemeral feature. Risang Waterfall is the waterfall that observed in the study area.

Fig 2.10 : Risang Waterfall

5. **Gully:** On a hillside, running water in monsoon season erodes the soil and makes gully. Several gullies were seen during the traversing in our fieldwork. These gullies remain wet during monsoon and dry during winter.(Fig 2.11)

Fig 2.11 : Gully

6. **Plunge pool :** A plunge pool is a deep pool of water under waterfall which is formed by the falling of water , rocks and other sediments from a high place. We observed this feature at Risang Waterfall. (Fig 2.12)

Fig 2.12 : Plunge Pool (Source:Google)

7. **Pothole** : A pothole is a spherical , bowl-shaped or irregular hollow that is usually deeper than wide. It formed by the erosion of rock , especially by the action of water. (Fig 2.13)

Fig 2.13: pothole

8. **Alutilla Cave**: A cave is a vast, naturally occurring underground void that can be explored by humans. In other words, a cave is a place, not an object, and practically any underground void in rock – whether filled with air or water. In our research, we discovered the Alutilla cave near the Changotang Anticline's axis. (Fig 2.14)

Fig 2.14: Alutilla Cave

9. **Load Cast** : Load casts are bulges, lumps, and lobes on sedimentary rock bedding planes. The lumps "hang down" from the upper layer into the bottom layer, and normally form with roughly uniform spacing. (Fig 2.15)

Fig 2.15: Load Cast

10. **Clay Ball** : They are balls of silt and clay, coated with a poorly sorted mixture of gravel and sand. In many cases they are nearly spherical in shape. (Fig 2.16)

Fig 2.16: Clay Balls

Chapter 3. Structure and Tectonics

3.1 Regional Tectonic Setup:

The Bengal basin (Fig 3.1) is fundamentally in between of three major tectonic provinces:

- Western Bengal Basin; near to Indian shield ,
- North-Eastern Bengal Basin
- Eastern Bengal Basin also known as Chittagong-Tripura Folded Belt.

The tectonic evolution of Bengal basin is basically related to the collision between Indian Plate with Burma and Tibetan Plates. The collision of these plates can be observed in two different forms : (1) The North – Northeasterly continent – continent collision of the Indian plate with Tibetan Plate , expressed as thrusting , lateral displacement and uplift related with the development of Eastern Himalayas and (2) The oblique subduction of the oceanic crust beneath the Burma plate , which resulted the development of accretionary wedges , which together with thrusting and folding has subsequently uplifted the Indo-Burman Ranges and associated fold belt of CTFB region (Fig 3.2) (Gani and Alam , 1999 ; Sikder and Alam , 2003).

Fig 3.1: Bengal Basin

Fig 3.2: Geological Structure of Bangladesh (Source: Wikipedia)

The geological traverse method and attitude of beds and satellite images along the Changotang anticline discloses that it is a long-narrow asymmetrical anticline with low angle crest, steeper flanks. The traversing was covered in three days. On first day the traversing was began from the part of western flank and covered the western flank on two days. And on last day traversing covered the eastern flank.

General dip direction of western flank differs from due west to $S78^{\circ}W$. The amount of dip varies from 20° to 40° . And in the eastern flank the beds dips most of the time at east direction. And the axis may be found somewhere between the vertical beds which were found while traversing.

3.2 Structural Mapping of Changotang :

The Changotang Anticline is basically a large scale anticline situated in Khagrachari trending NNW-SSE direction and is an asymmetrical anticline. The western flank of the anticline is long and the eastern flank of the anticline is shorter than the western flank. The longer western flank and the shorter eastern flank is formed as a result of major thrust fault in the western flank and subsequent erosion over a long period of time.

During the fieldwork on “Changotang Anticline, Along Matiranga-Khagrachari Road cut Section”, many structures were found. Some of the structures are described below:

1. **Fold:** The Changotang is an asymmetrical anticlinal fold and the western flank is longer than the eastern flank.

2. **Fault:** In the study area, there is a thrust fault trending East West which is cut across the folded structure. The longer western flank and shorter eastern flank is due to the presence of thrust fault. Some micro fault also observed in the study area.

3. **Joints :** Joint is a break in rock mass where there have been no relative movement on opposite sides of the rock. There are many joints in several section of this anticline. Vertical joints were more common on the field area. (Fig 3.4 : Joint)

Fig 3.4 : Joint

4. **Unconformity** : An unconformity is a surface of erosion or non deposition which separates the younger strata from the older one. On the study area we found many unconformity structure which was characterized by abnormal change in grain size. Started with fine grain sediments in the bottom and suddenly gravel sized materials at the top. such feature resembles that the velocity of the flow was very high when they carried bigger sized rocks. But after losing there velocity gradually these gravel sized materials tends to deposit over finer grained sediments as the middle layer eroded by certain action.

5. **Drag Fold** : Drag fold is formed in an incompetent bed lying between two competent beds which is formed by the movement of the competent beds in the opposite directions relative to one another. In the study area , some drag folds were observed in some sections but there was no well exposed drag fold to observed.

6. **Crisscross joint** : A crisscross is one kind of joint which are approximately perpendicular to fold axes. A crisscross joint indicates tectonic activity.

Chapter 4. Sedimentology and Stratigraphy

4.1 Facies analysis and Interpretation

A rock facies is a grouping of rocks that share certain features.

There could be one bed or several beds. Ideally, it would be a unique rock that originated as a result of a specific process, set of conditions, or environment during sedimentation.

SL.	Lithofacies	Texture	Sedimentary Feature	Interpretation
1.	Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone	Very fine to fine sand with alternating silt	Ripple-cross lamination	Bi-directional channel lag deposit at shallow water environment
2.	Bouma sequence	Very fine to fine sand	Graded- flat - ripple-parallel bedding/ lamination, complete or incomplete	Deep marine turbidite environment
3.	Parallel laminated silty shale	Silty shale to shale	Parallel lamination	Product of lower flow regime of tidal environment in low flow condition
4.	Massive sand	Medium to fine grained sand	Massive structure with slumping.	Fluvial environment.
5.	Trough cross bedded sandstone	Medium to fine grained, yellowish-brown sand	Trough cross bedding	Fluvial environment
6.	Laminated Shale with Nodular Structure	Bluish gray shale with nodules	Parallel lamination	Deep marine environment
7.	Heterolithic Facies	Very fine to fine sand and mud	Fining upward sequence	Deposited in shallow marine to intertidal flat environment

8.	Trough cross bedded calcareous sandstone	Medium to fine grained, yellowish-brown sand	Trough cross bedding , cementing material as calcareous	Fluvial environment
9.	Flaser laminated sandstone with minor mud	Very fine grained, yellowish sand and silt to clay sized mud	Flaser lamination	Deposition in current activity in tidal environment
10.	Ripple laminated sandstone	Fine to very fine- grained sand and silt	Ripple lamination	Produced in abandoned part of channel or shallow water inter-tidal environment
11.	Lenticular laminated sandstone	Medium to fine grained sand and mud.	Cross lamination, lenticular bedding	Ripple movement with mud deposition in lower tidal flat environment

Table4.1.: Facies analysis and Interpretation

Lithofacies Description :

i. Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone:

Ripple and ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone lithofacies are yellow colored, fine grained sandstone. This facies is especially common in the studied region. This is especially true with ripples, which are never perfectly symmetrical. This facies evolved as a result of the movement of small waves. This occurs in the thalweg's shallower regions, where smaller channels meet larger ones. In Fig 4.1. & Fig 4.2 we can see ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone an the Log 4.1

Litholog 4.1 : Litholog of Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone

Fig 4.1 : Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone

Fig 4.2 : Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone

ii. Bouma sequence:

Channelized sandstones can be seen across the entirety of the Bouma series. Beginning with massive graded sandstone, the sequence continues upward over parallel laminated sandstone, ripple laminated sandstone, cross laminated sandstone, parallel laminated siltstone, and finally massive mud. In general, a sequence like this one suggests a marine Environment. In Fig 4.3 we can see Bouma sequence and the litholog in Litholog 4.2

Litholog 4.2 : Litholog of Bouma sequence

Fig 4.3 : Bouma sequence

iii. Parallel laminated silty shale:

We found sandstone in this facies that was bedded and had thin mud layers. These sandstones range from yellowish brown to a fine grain gray in color. In Fig 4.4 & Fig 4.5 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.3.

Litholog 4.3 :Litholog of Parallel laminated silty shale

Fig 4.4 : Parallel laminated silty shale (i)

Fig 4.5 : Parallel laminated silty shale(ii)

iv. **Massive sand:**

Sand that ranged from medium to fine grains and had a yellowish hue was found in this facies. This occurs frequently in environments dominated by fluvial processes. (Fig 4.6) the litholog in Litholog 4.4

Litholog 4.4 :Litholog of Massive Sandstone

Fig 4.7 : Massive Sandstone(ii)

Fig 4.6 : Massive Sandstone(i)

v. Trough cross bedded sandstone:

This facies is made up of layers of fine to medium sand with very few layers of mud. The presence of this facies suggests that sediments were deposited in a fluvial environment. In Fig 4.8 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.5 .

Litholog 4.5 : Litholog of trough cross bedded sandstone

Fig 4.8 : Trough cross bedded sandstone

vi. Laminated Shale with Nodular Structure:

We found compact shale that had a grainy encrustation of iron that ranged from medium to coarse. After 15 meters, we noticed that the mud had laminated. This suggests that situations are relatively calm within a reducing environment. This reflects the most recent marine transgression in the state of the marine environment. We also observed nodular structure there. In Fig 4.9 & Fig 4.10 we can see Laminated Shale and litholog in Litholog 4.6

Litholog 4.6 : Litholog of Laminated Shale

Fig 4.9 : Laminated Shale

Fig 4.10 : Laminated Shale

vii. Heterolithic Facies:

Heterolithic Facies consists of flexure bedding, lenticular bedding and wavy bedding. It suggests its deposition in shallow marine to intertidal flat environments (De Reaf, 1977; Reineck and Singh, 1980). This is an appropriate example of tidal environment. In Fig 4.11 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.7

Log 4.7 : Litholog of Heterolithic Facies

Fig 4.11 : Heterolithic Facies

viii. Trough cross bedded calcareous sandstone:

This facies is made up of layers of fine to medium sand. We found the cementing material as calcareous by studying the exposure. The presence of this facies suggests that sediments were deposited in a fluvial environment. In Fig 4.4 & Fig 4.5 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.3

Log 4.8 : Litholog of Trough cross bedded calcareous sandstone

Fig 4.12 : Trough cross bedded calcareous sandstone

ix. Flaser laminated sandstone with minor mud:

In this facies, there is flaser laminated sandstone with very fine grains and a yellow color. These facies were deposited in alternating period of current activity with stand still period for deposition of clay. In Fig 4.13 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.9.

Log 4.9 : Litholog of flaser laminated sandstone

Fig 4.13 : Flaser laminated sandstone with minor mud

x. Ripple laminated sandstone:

The most common type of rock in the Bokabil Formation is ripple laminated sandstone. We saw graded bedding sand with ripples that went in both directions. This is because flow in a tidal environment can go in both directions. This happens a lot in places with shallow tide. In Fig 4.14 we can see Ripple laminated sandstone and litholog in Litholog 4.10

Log 4.10 : Litholog of Ripple laminated sandstone

Fig 4.14 : Ripple laminated sandstone

xi. Lenticular laminated sandstone:

In these facies, we observed bi-convex shaped lenses of sandstones. This was mostly current generated and sediment supply was deficient. This facies is commonly observed in fine grained part of heterolithic facies and it indicates larger period of stagnant with occasional current activity. . In Fig 4.15 we can see Parallel laminated silty shale and litholog in Litholog 4.11

Log 4.11 : Litholog of Lenticular laminated sandstone

Fig 4.15 : Lenticular laminated sandstone

4.2: Local Litho-stratigraphy subdivision

UNIT	Thickness	Major Facies	Description	Depositional Environment
UNIT-1	120+ meters (Top Eroded/Partly Eroded)	i. Trough Cross Bedded Sandstone ii. Massive Sand	Medium to fine grained, yellowish brown colored sand with few mud layers	From our observations, the depositional environment is fluvial.
UNIT-2	1000 meters	i. Flaser laminated sandstone with minor mud ii. Lenticular laminated sandstone iii. Parallel laminated silty shale iv. Ripple laminated sandstone v. Heterolithic Facies vi. Laminated Shale with Nodular Structure vii. Trough cross bedded calcareous sandstone	Very fine to fine grained, yellowish colored sand with alternation of sand and mud. Presence of fining upward tidal sequence and laminated shale which is fissile in nature	As per our observations, it indicates fluviodeltaic environment.
UNIT-3	180+ meters (Base not seen)	i. Ripple cross-laminated sandstone-siltstone ii. Bouma sequence	Very fine to fine grained sandstone, sand-mud alternation and intraformational conglomerate, clay balls are present.	Our observation particularly suggest that, the unit was deposited under deep marine to deltaic environment.

Table 4.2: Local Litho-stratigraphy subdivision

4.3 Stratigraphy of the Fold Belt in Bangladesh

Age	Group	Formation	Rock Type
Pleistocene		Modhupur Clay	Mottled clay
Plio-Pleistocene	Tipam	Dupi Tila	Predominantly sandstone with minor shale and clay beds
		Girujan Clay	Mainly shale
Pliocene		Tipam Sandstone	Predominantly sandstone with minor shale
Mio-Pliocene	Surma	Bokabil	Alternating shale and sandstone with minor siltstone
Miocene		Bhuban	Alternating sandstone and shale with minor conglomerate
Oligocene	Barail	Renji	Predominantly Sandstone (pink) with minor shale
		Jenum	Predominantly shale with minor siltstone

Base not encountered

Table 4.3: Stratigraphic succession of Fold Belt in Bangladesh (source: Badrul Imam 2013, Energy Resources of Bangladesh)

4.4. Co-relation and Comparison

Studied Area		Stratigraphy of Fold-Belt of Bangladesh			
Unit	Lithology	Group	Formation	Lithology	Age
???	Not Seen	Tipam	Dupitila	Predominantly sandstone with minor shale and clay beds	Plio-Pliostocene
	Not seen		Girujan Clay	Mainly Shale	
Unit-1	Medium to fine grained, yellowish brown colored sand with few mud layers		Tipam Sandstone	Predominantly sandstone with minor shale	Pliocene
Unit-3	Very fine to fine grained, yellowish colored sand with alternation of sand and mud. Presence of fining upward tidal sequence and and laminated shale which is fissile in nature	Surma	Bokabil	Alternating shale and sandstone with minor siltstone	Mio-Pliocene
Unit-4	Very fine to fine grained sandstone, sand-mud alternation and intraformational conglomerate, clay balls are present		Bhuban	Alternating sandstone and shale with minor conglomerate	Miocene
????	Not seen	Barail	Renji	Predominantly sandstone(pink) with minor shale	Oligocene

Table 4.4: Co-relation and Comparison

Litholog 4.4.1 : Western Flank

Litholog 4.4.2 : Eastern Flank

5. Economic Geo Resources of the study area

As far as can be determined, the study region contains no substantial mineral deposits. During fieldwork in the region, hard mudstone, shale, sandstone, etc. were discovered. Among these, mudstone, hard shale, and sandstone(Fig 5.3) are significant building materials.

In the researched area, a vast quantity of pebbles(Fig 5.5) and stones are discovered. These are utilized for building construction, railway blasts, and road and highway construction materials.

Our research area's surface water sources consist of the Chengi River(Fig 5.1), precipitation, and chara (Dhoillachara, Thakurchara etc.).

Chengi River is a Perennial River because it contains water throughout the year. The charas are dry during the winter. In Khagrachari, the residential and agricultural water supply is dependent on groundwater because fresh surface water for domestic use and irrigation is somewhat sparse. This groundwater is sourced from an underground aquifer. While The majority of the people living on the hills rely on surface water.

Fig 5.1: Chengi River

Fig 5.2 :Direct circulation fluid rotary

Fig 5.3: Sandstone collected from an exposure

Fig 5.4: Sands collected from an exposure

Fig 5.5: A vast quantity of pebbles

Fig 5.6: Risang Waterfall

6. Conclusion

The geological and lithological studies of the Changotang anticline, Khagrachari were investigated during this fieldwork. This report details the findings as well as the additional inquiry that was conducted following this fieldwork.

The Changotang anticline is located in Bangladesh's eastern fold belt. It is a thrust-faulted anticline. The Indo-Burman subduction zone's compressional tectonics dominate this structure. This anticline stratigraphically comprises (from oldest to youngest) the Surma group, the Tipam group, the Dupitila formation, and recent alluvium. Nonetheless, there was considerable difficulty in correlating our stratigraphy with Evan's. Consequently, the tertiary stratigraphy of this region and Bangladesh must be rewritten.

Shale, silty shale, sandy shale, sandstone, and mudstone are the dominant sedimentary rock types in this area. Bedding, cross bedding, lenticular bedding, lamination, cross lamination, wavy bedding, clay galls, nodular formations, and many more forms of sedimentary structures have been observed here. A thick layer of alluvium formed here as a result of weathering as well.

From a geological point of view, however, it might be the ideal location for the discovery of commercial resources. In order to determine whether or not this region contains oil and gas, it is required to conduct the appropriate research. The Changotang anticline is a fantastic location for conducting in-depth research, which necessitates more resources, including more time, more equipment, and a broader understanding.

7. References

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